

STRATEGIES FOR PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF A GENDER APPROACH

SHARIFZODA SARDORBЕК O'ROZBOY TABIB O'G'LI

Urganch State Pedagogical Institute

Dean of the Faculty of Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854298>

Abstract: In this article in the preparation of students for pedagogical activity, feedback was made on the scientific and theoretical features of preparatory strategies based on the gender approach.

Key words: gender preparedness, gender approach, gender socialization, gender reality, gender competence.

It is known that the *"XXI century is the century towards an informed society"*. In all periods of the development of society, the intellectualization of the educational system was considered a requirement of the period. The modern educational process requires teachers to know perfectly both intellectual knowledge, potential and ways to explain it to students. President Of Our Republic Sh.M.As Mirziyoev noted, *"In order to renew and modernize our country today, develop it on an innovative basis, carry out the multifaceted and complex tasks set before us, we entrust important tasks in the management of the state and society to modern and creatively thinking, capable of taking responsibility in any situation, with a high intellectual potential, patriotic young personnel"*¹. Not only a separate person, but also the intellectual potential of the whole society is gaining importance in the context of globalization and the fact that economic development is not going smoothly.

The demand of today's times requires future teachers to keep up with the Times and always work hard on their scientific potential, creativity, self-esteem. Therefore, in the preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity, it is necessary to analyze the scientific characteristics of the gender approach and prepare the future oedagog personnel for scientific and practical activities.

In higher education institutions, the preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity on the basis of a gender approach is a complex process, the rational implementation of which serves to ensure the professional maturity of future teachers. We know that the training of personnel in a particular specialty is carried out on the basis of educational standards, regulatory documents, a system of educational and methodological literature. The concept of a Gender approach refers to human activity, being its carrier is the subject. Such opportunities are created by society during its historical development, determined by the unity of various factors and a set of their interaction. Human activity is a process of potential exploitation. When a person has the necessary knowledge and qualifications, that is, the potential that allows him to perform his work qualitatively, then he is considered a specialist and a master of his profession. This is an extremely important condition. Because intellectual potential is associated with the expectation of processes that can always occur. In the simplest case, if a

¹ Address of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Supreme Assembly // people's word, December 29, 2018

person does not justify trust in him, this means that either he was harassed, or his potential was misjudged. It should be noted that the gender approach in education is a rather complex concept.

The preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity on the basis of education on the basis of a gender approach gives the following results:

First of all, on the basis of education, the means and systems of training will become the basis for serving future learners to train personnel who can keep up with the Times, meeting their requirements for professional activities.

Secondly, on the basis of the use of pedagogical educational stages developed to prepare future teachers for professional activities in practical activities, it will be possible to achieve high efficiency in education by achieving a new quality indicator, and it will also be possible to prepare learners to make modern innovative approaches.

Thirdly, it helps future teachers to develop pedagogical creativity, erudition, capacity building on related subjects and the qualities of being an active member of the innovative process. The Gender strategy demonstrates the importance of reforming the educational system taking into account gender-oriented programs, expanding the possibilities of genders for free spiritual development, emphasizing the need to include the gender component in the educational standards of all higher education specialties. The Gender approach is seen as one of the ways to form a personality that meets world standards.

The main idea of the gender approach in education is to take into account all the factors of the educational process: the content, forms and methods of education, technologies for organizing the educational process, pedagogical communication, as well as the peculiarities of interaction with the development of representatives of the male and female gender of traditional gender stereotypes. The gender approach to direct personality education is aimed at creating favorable conditions for the upbringing of boys and girls, in which their development and spiritual and value orientation contribute to the positive and harmonious formation of individual male, female and androgynous traits, the interaction of effective sexual roles in society.

Thus, the gender approach in education is aimed at expanding the possibilities of students to manifest individual gender characteristics, freely expressing and developing qualities that can go beyond gender stereotypes, which contributes to the successful gender socialization, self-awareness and self-awareness of the individual. The most important task of the modern educational system is to improve the process of socialization of the younger generation, in particular, gender socialization. We see gender socialization as a process of personality formation and self-development, carried out in the system of relations with adults, peers and oneself in accordance with individual gender characteristics and characteristics.

The higher education system is the main model of the social world, where students act as subjects of social relations, and the skills of interaction with people of different sexes develop. It is in the process of gender socialization that gender stereotypes are strengthened in the child's mind, models of behavior are developed, which determine the success of interaction with the outside world and the individual possibilities of personal and professional improvement.

It is necessary to diagnose the real state of pedagogical reality in order to ensure the process of socialization of future teachers and to organize the targeted preparation of the future

teacher for the implementation of a gender approach in professional activities. The following methods were used to carry out the corresponding study:

Gender identity tests: one gender role questionnaire, the Freiburg personality questionnaire (Fpi), the Liri test, which identifies personality types and determines the severity of male, female characteristics; allows you to study gender characteristics and characteristics in the personality structure; the "proverbs" questionnaire for studying gender relationships of students, problem questionnaires.

Obviously, it is possible to improve the quality of gender education of the future teacher and achieve his readiness to implement a gender approach in professional activities only in the construction of his professional training as a holistic system, including the principles and pedagogical conditions for the formation of gender competence of the teacher.

We consider and define gender competence as a unit of knowledge, skills, targeted pedagogical actions for the implementation of skills and experiences of the implementation of the gender approach, gender socialization and gender strategy in order to fully reveal and implement the uniqueness of each student's personality in the context of a holistic pedagogical process. Among the principles for the formation of gender competence of future teachers, which affect the effectiveness of the system, are the principles of differentiation of content and the organization of the formation of gender competence taking into account the gender characteristics of students; interdisciplinary integration of the content and technologies of the formation of gender competence of the teacher; compliance of gender education technologies

In conclusion, it should be noted that improving the quality of gender education and purposeful preparation of the future teacher for the implementation of a gender approach in professional activities can be considered as an important direction for improving higher pedagogical education.

References:

1. Resolution No. 187 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 6, 2017 "On approval of state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017. Issue 14, Article 230.
2. Gender strategy of the Russian Federation (Project). - M., 2004. - 25 p.
3. Mydrik, A.B. About gender (gender) approach in social education /A.V. Mydrik // Educational care at school. - 2003. - No. 5. - C. 15 - 19.
4. Nadolinskaya, L.N. The influence of gender stereotypes on upbringing and parenting /L.N. Nadolinsky // Pedagogy. - 2004. - No. 5. - C. 30 - 35.
5. Reshetnikov, P. Gender schools /P. Reshetnikov // Narodnoe obozrenie. - 2007. - No. 1. - C. 217 - 220.
6. Sharifzoda S. Integrative methods of formation of basic competencies in students. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation; 32(3) ISSN 2651-4451 | e-ISSN 2651-446X (2021)
7. S.O. Sharifzada. Mechanisms of using an integrative approach in the formation of basic competencies in students: a dissertation written for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD). Bukhara. - 2022.

8.Sharifzoda S. The use of an integrative approach in the formation of basic competencies in students as a socio-didactic necessity // Journal of critical reviews ISSN- 2394-5125 vol 7, issue 12, 2020 3115.

